

Speculation on the Presence of Environment and Particle Systems in the E,B Fields of a Moving Charge Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the process of accelerating a charged particle involves three systems, the force system, the particle system (including bound E electric and B magnetic fields) and the environment. Two of these systems are associated with measurables which may change sign, namely F and v , dv/dt (where v is velocity) and F always acts on the particle system, even if it is at rest. This is associated with the usual idea, for a conservative force, of potential energy converted into kinetic etc. The surprise, so to speak, in the accelerated charge system is that it involves three instead of two systems, with work from F being lost as radiated photons to the environment. The environment has no measurable which changes sign and so can receive energy which is lost to the force-particle system. We argued that this represents a thermodynamic system with entropy being produced.

Here we try to examine the presence of the environment in a different manner. In fact, we argue that the environment is already present in the electrostatic case, which differs from a usual particle at rest. As a result, the environment does not disappear.

We first note that an uncharged particle has inertia (proportional to rest mass) which a force must overcome in order to accelerate the particle. A charged particle at rest has rest mass as well as electrostatic self-energy, $.5\epsilon_0 EE$. This is part of rest mass and inertia and force must act on it to set the charged particle in motion. There may, however, be the presence of another inertial type force, because the charge system, assumed to have a large rest mass, may act on a low rest mass test charge q_1 at some distance l along the x axis, for example. The test charge is held in place and so the E field of the large mass system exerts a force q_1E on q_1 and by action-reaction, an identical force is felt by the large rest mass system. This is like an additional inertial mass for the force trying to accelerate the large rest mass system. Thus, the force must act not only on the inertial mass pieces of the large rest mass ($m_0 + .5\epsilon_0 EE$), but also on the force in the environment, q_1E . The action of the force on $.5\epsilon_0 EE$ and q_1E need not be the same. In particular, $\text{grad dot } E = \text{charge density}/\epsilon_0$ focuses on the charge within a volume, but we argued in Part I that one may have pieces of E such that $\text{grad dot } E = 0$. These pieces need not die down like $1/r$ pieces needed to balance $4\pi r^2$ of the surface area of a sphere (Stoke's law). They may be associated, we argue, with force (presumably a function of acceleration) acting on q_1 , i.e. yielding a piece of E which acts on q_1 in a manner which is different from the usual $1/r$ E term.

In other words, the force automatically acts on two systems, the particle system (with bound E, B fields dropping as $1/r$) and the environment which may have test charges. Work may be done in both and energy transferred. The energy transferred to the environment (radiated photons) is considered entropy production, but seems that it should be expected given the fact that the E field of an electrostatic charge is associated with both rest mass, $.5\epsilon_0 EE$, and force E on a test charge q_1 in the environment.

Newtonian Mechanics for a Conservative Force

As noted in Part I, Newtonian mechanics for a conservative force involves the interchange of potential energy linked to a force with kinetic energy of a particle-system. The environment does not come into play. This is the usual scenario. Thus, when a third system appears, namely the environment, which may absorb energy which does not come back to the particle system, one classifies this as a different scenario, namely thermodynamics, and argues that entropy is being produced.

A question which arises is: Why should the environment system come into play? We first consider the case of a frictional force. This force, unlike $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$, is velocity dependent. If the particle does not move and there are no other forces parallel to the frictional force, then it is zero. Thus, there can be no potential-kinetic energy interchange. For a conservative force acting against the direction of motion, the particle slows down, losing kinetic energy, and comes to a stop. At that instant, the usual force still exists and acts on the particle in the negative x direction, creating kinetic energy in the opposite direction. One states that potential energy is being converted back into kinetic and one has time reversal symmetry. For a particle slowing down due to friction, when it stops, friction does not cause it to accelerate in the opposite direction. It has lost its kinetic energy, presumably to the environment, and the frictional force cannot return it. There is a different kind of symmetry.

A second example is an accelerating charge which we try to examine in the next section.

Accelerating Charge and the Presence of an Environment

Consider a charge with a large rest mass which is at rest. This may be viewed in two ways. First, one has a particle-bound E electric field system with inertial energy:

$$\text{Inertial energy of a rest charge} = m_{\text{occ}} + .5e_0 EE \quad ((1))$$

Here m_0 is the rest mass of the core of the charge Q , ignoring the self-energy of the electric field. It is often shown that the self-energy expression may be obtained by starting with no charge at an origin and bringing in thin spherical shells (to the origin) thus building up a sphere of uniform charge. The core produces an electric field E_1 which acts on the charge of the sphere, but when the sphere arrives at the origin, it is bound there and energy stored as permanent potential energy, i.e. self-energy. Ultimately, this becomes $.5 e_0 EE$. Thus, even though there is a self-energy due to the electrostatic field, it is really bound work done by the less than Q core acting on charged shells being brought in, i.e. on the environment. This energy is then trapped.

This is equivalent to the notion that:

$$F = q_1 E + q_1 v \times B \quad ((2)) \quad \text{i.e. Lorentz's force}$$

In other words, if Q is not moving and there is no external B , then a test charge q_1 , in the environment, feels a force $q_1 E$.

Furthermore, there may be interchange of energy with this test charge. If one ignores radiation effects (which are tiny), a charge q_1 in the environment may lose kinetic energy to potential energy while approaching Q (Q and q_1 have the same sign), but when it stops, it is pushed outward and gains the energy back. Thus, the charge system Q is really releasing energy to the environment, it is just that this energy came from the environment in the first place, namely in the form of kinetic energy.

The question becomes: What happens if one tries to accelerate the Q charge system? As in usual Newtonian mechanics, this system has inertia proportional to inertia ((1)), which is trapped potential energy. Force must act on both m_0 and $.5\epsilon_0 E E$. As the particle starts to move,

$$.5\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0) \longrightarrow .5\epsilon_0 E(v)E(v) + .5/u_0 B(v)B(v) \quad ((3))$$

The charge Q , however, may also be exerting a force, $q_1 E(v=0)$ on a test charge q_1 some distance l away along the x axis, with the assumption that Q is going to move along the x -axis. If q_1 is fixed in place by another force, then there is an equal action-reaction force $q_1 E(v=0)$ on Q which acts as a hindrance (i.e. inertia) to the force trying to accelerate Q . Thus, given the fact that an electric field renders a force (which is the reason there is an extra rest mass of $.5\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)$ in the first place), a force trying to accelerate Q with its bound $E(v=0)$ field, may also act on a test charge. Work is done on Q and its bound E , B rest mass pieces, but also may be done on the test charge, meaning that energy is necessarily "lost" to the environment.

One may argue that if one removes the test charge q_1 , then this argument fails, but without the notion of a test charge, it seems there is no notion of an electric field at a point.

One may note that $\text{grad dot } E = \text{charge density}(r' \text{ vector}, t - R/c) / \epsilon_0 \quad ((4))$

Here $t - R/c$ is retarded time, where $R = |r \text{ vector} - r' \text{ vector}|$, with $r \text{ vector}$, measured from a fixed origin, to a measurement point and $r' \text{ vector}$, from the same fixed origin to a piece of charge. We argued in Part I that one may have E pieces such that $\text{grad dot } E = 0$. In particular, grad in such a case may act on dipole moment terms instead of $1/r$ terms in the denominator.

To clarify, the electric field is shown in (1) (pp 458-59) to be:

$$E(r \text{ vector}, t) = -u_0 / (4 * 3.14) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dp}{dt} (t - r/c) + 1 / (4 * 3.14) \frac{r \text{ dot } d}{dt} \frac{dp}{dt} (t - r/c) \frac{r \text{ vector}}{(c r r r)} \quad ((5))$$

where $c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 u_0}$

Grad may act on $1/\{r \text{ power}(n)\}$ terms or on $d/dt dp/dt$ where p is the dipole moment. Acting on the dipole moment yields zero as we showed in Part I. Thus, there are pieces of E associated with $1/r$ drop-off instead of the $1/r^2$ drop-off of field pieces which are still bound to Q . These pieces are part of the usual mass energy $.5\epsilon_0 E(v)E(v) + .5/u_0 B(v)B(v)$, while the other E pieces act on the environment so to speak, i.e. are not bound to Q , but may release energy to the environment. Thus, the accelerating force is doing two kinds of work, pumping energy into

the Q (with bound E,B) in the form of kinetic energy and pumping energy into the environment as radiated photons. The momentum flux into the environment may be explicitly calculated using:

$$\text{Integral volume } \text{grad dot } (C^2 \text{ ExB}) \quad ((6))$$

where one uses E and B terms which drop as $1/r$. Converting to a surface area of a sphere one sees that ExB goes as $1/(r^2)$ and the sphere surface area as $4\pi r^2$, so electromagnetic momentum flux goes into the environment.

As a result, the E field (and B) is not only part of internal rest mass of the Q charge (i.e. the bound pieces of E,B which drop as $1/(r^2)$ or faster), but also part of a force field acting on test charges in the environment. Thus, it seems natural that some energy of an accelerating force goes to the charge system and some other to the environment. It is only if one considers the Newtonian case of a rest mass with no force acting on the environment, that one has the notion of only a force-particle system. In the radiating case, one may say that entropy is being produced and energy lost to the environment, but that is a particle-centric viewpoint it seems. The situation is that the particle-force systems are coupled in a different way than the force-E,B fields which drop as $1/r$. In other words, the force always acts on Q and its bound E,B, but the radiated photons escape and are no longer under the influence of the force. It is just used to produce them, like friction produces heat.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that an electrostatic charge at rest already manifests two different aspects of the electric field. In one case, $\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)$ represents self-energy which is rest mass, but there is still a force exerted by E on a test charge in the environment. This second aspect and the notion of environment may then not be ignored, we argue.

If a force tries to accelerate the rest mass and bound $\epsilon_0 E(v=0)E(v=0)$, it should also have an effect on E acting as a force on a test charge q_1 in the environment. These two effects need not be the same. In other words, $\text{grad dot } E = \text{charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t-r/c) / \epsilon_0$, uses retarded time and grad may act on either $1/(r^{\text{power}(n)})$ terms or on $t-r/c$. If grad acts on $t-r/c$ terms, linked with v and dv/t , then these E1 pieces yield $\text{grad dot } E_1=0$, as shown in Part I. They are not bound to Q. They are E1 pieces associated with the environment. Thus, the force pumps kinetic energy into the charge plus bound E(v), B(v) system as well as into the environment, because there must be E, B field in the environment to deal with test charges. The energy pumped to the environment, however, is in the form of radiated photons and is lost, just like heat generated from friction is lost from a particle system. An accelerating charge system seems to be a prototype of thermodynamics because it shows that $d\text{Work}$ is linked to two terms, dE (the particle system) and TdS , the environment. The usual conservative force Newtonian picture involves $dE=d\text{Work}$.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory 3rd Edition) Addison-Wesely 1980